

PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN A CORPORATE UNIVERSITY AND A TRADITIONAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The sustainability of an organization depends on its ability to develop the skills of its employees, promoting innovation, which in turn leads to improved organizational performance. With the advancement of technology in the business world, many organizations have tried to upgrade the skills of their employees to improve the efficiency of the organization.

The current socio-economic environment is characterized by extremely fast and competitive evolutionary dynamics. Accordingly, firms must implement training plans to improve their competitiveness. This has a profound impact on industries where competition is particularly fierce and requires vigorous approaches to improving the quality of corporate learning to adapt to, or even anticipate, profound technological, cultural, and social challenges. Thus, greater flexibility and social intelligence are needed to solve these complex problems, requiring the development and strengthening of human capital.

In summary, the partnership between corporate and traditional universities stands as a vital instrument for driving educational and economic progress. By bridging the gap between theory and practice, these collaborations have the potential to empower individuals and organizations alike, ushering in a new era of education and workforce development.

Keywords: education, corporate training, traditional universities, competitiveness, partnership.

Main text of the article. Partnerships between corporations and universities can offer the best of both worlds. Traditional business schools can create new opportunities for themselves by meeting companies' needs for rapidly changing skills, and corporate training departments can benefit from structured links with universities and colleges [1]. An example of a university-corporate partnership is the Tennessee Valley Authority, an electricity provider in the southeastern United States, which created its own corporate university, TVA University. CEO Katie Hammond and her team provide internal training to employees:

Previously, education and training were viewed as expenses. Today, training is considered an investment [2]. She and her team have done extensive work measuring the effectiveness of training in education, duplication of work/training, behavioral changes, and the value of training for current work. Although most of their training is done in-house, they also partner with the University of Tennessee at Chattanooga (UTC) to provide an Executive program MBA to their managers and executives who were targeted for promotion as part of their corporate succession plan.

As with the TVA / UTC partnership, a survey conducted at Corporate University Xchange, found that about 62 percent of corporate universities have partnerships with four-year colleges, and that share is expected to increase to 85 percent. Often this alliance is intended to legitimize courses, increase confidence, meet employee needs, and provide necessary knowledge in specific areas of study. In some cases, training staff may not have expertise or experience in specialized or advanced areas. Other benefits often include reduced program costs and freeing up HR trainers for other tasks [3].

Corporate universities are not a comprehensive solution. Some, even in high-tech sectors, believe that the missing piece is more a function of long-term performance rather than short-term needs for innovative, in-

demand products. These critics believe that they can only give part of the answer and that the traditional university is best suited for more well-rounded people who can see the big picture [4].

Real costs also need to be taken into account when designing a corporate university. Xchange Corporate University surveyed 120 corporate university deans and found that 64% of them currently conduct less than 20% of their teaching and learning using technology. However, this proportion is expected to grow rapidly and education will be delivered through one of five key technologies: intranets, satellites, the Internet, video conferencing and CD-ROM. Other technology alternatives may include video, audio, computer applications, video streaming, desktop computers, extranets, direct satellite communication to the home or office, and electronic productivity support [5].

Cost remains a complex issue when designing corporate universities and depends on the technology used and class size, as well as the needs of the participants. There is general agreement that online training should always be cheaper than an equivalent course delivered in a classroom, but it should be based on both quality and cost. An inexpensive course can be designed for live chat sessions; however, if the course must be interactive and use streaming video, audio, and synchronous and asynchronous learning, the price will increase. The costs for setup, equipment, technical support and training are initially very high. Other costs to consider include online library costs, online materials, faculty development, software, training, classrooms, computers for all participants, modern instructor podiums, light chamber, advanced equipment, increased security, frequent updates, maintenance and life cycle costs [6].

Savings, however, can be achieved by reducing travel time and costs as employees can learn while on the job. Training can be conducted during slow periods or scheduled within the workday. Custom Web-based

learning materials can be instantly updated and modified to minimize waste and reprinting costs [7]. There are systems that provide instant communication of test results to allow instructors and participants to immediately assess their knowledge.

Motivations for Partnership

Mutual Knowledge Exchange: One of the key motivations for this partnership is the exchange of knowledge and expertise. Corporate universities bring real-world insights and practical experience to the table, while traditional universities offer a strong academic foundation and research capabilities. By pooling their resources, these institutions create a more comprehensive educational environment.

Skill Development: The partnership allows for the development of programs that are tailored to the needs of the job market. Corporate universities often have a deep understanding of the specific skills and competencies required by industries. This insight, combined with the academic rigor of traditional universities, results in graduates who are well-prepared for the workforce.

Workforce Readiness: Employers today seek graduates who are not only academically proficient but also possess the ability to apply their knowledge in practical settings. This partnership focuses on producing graduates who are work-ready and can seamlessly transition into their chosen careers.

Traditional universities are facing competition from corporate universities, and many of them are actively joining partnerships with corporate universities to put an end to revenue losses. Others were under pressure to “professionalize” their mission and eliminate or change underfunded programs in favor of introductory, service-based, and scientific curriculum. There is currently debate over the university curriculum, and often commercial interests conflict with the university curriculum [8]. Universities are struggling to prevent liberal arts curricula from being swamped by technology and science [9]. Colleges and universities have been criticized for selling out to corporate America as business training grounds and turning college presidents into full-time fundraisers who are more like CEOs than academic leaders [10].

Corporate universities can either threaten or provide opportunities for traditional universities. Many universities are increasing the number of distance education programs. Between 1995 and 1998 alone, the number of distance learning programs increased by 72% [11]. Business schools at traditional universities are a key group seeking to become more relevant and responsive to corporate needs. Universities are also looking for ways to recoup money lost due to fewer students seeking traditional degrees. The pool of adult students is now larger than the traditional 18- to 24-year-old college market and is expected to grow. To serve non-traditional students, universities must now compete with corporate universities, certificate programs, virtual universities, and even for-profit education firms [12].

It should be noted in the surveys that should be taken into account when planning a corporate university:

- Does your organization have a specific problem that needs to be solved? Can these issues or problems be resolved with the help of a corporate university?
- How do you see a corporate university? A group of people? Online training? Will there be a faculty?
 - Will students be certified?
 - Is the progress of participating students tracked? How will you measure success?
 - Can you provide critical training?
 - Will the costs be lower than if the training took place at a traditional university?
 - Do you have staff (or can you use staff) to write course content, develop training materials, develop curriculum and pathways, deliver materials and evaluate results?
 - Can you provide the services yourself or will you also collaborate with commercial firms?

Through corporate partnerships, traditional universities meet the needs of adult students who have left university programs. Since universities already have many, if not all, of the facilities needed for distance learning, corporations can rely on these classes to save on the costs and learning curve associated with implementing new distance learning technology.

Universities will continue to be a great source of knowledge for corporate universities as more e-commerce courses and other courses related to current business issues are being added. In addition, corporations would be required to partner with existing colleges to offer transferable college credits toward degrees [13].

As the future of corporate universities includes more online learning as well as the challenge of keeping pace with evolving technologies, accreditation and program evaluation will become more important to ensure the credibility and legitimacy of corporate universities. Both employees and employers will find it necessary to identify certified programs that are effective as degree programs continue to proliferate at corporate universities and through corporate and traditional university partnerships [14]. Accreditation agencies will struggle with quality and student learning as more corporate universities seek equivalent university and professional credentials.

The research directions of corporate universities will go hand in hand with the future directions of corporate universities. Assessments of student learning, program goals, and cost-effectiveness will be important, as will the ability to achieve the organization's strategic goals.

While the partnership between corporate and traditional universities holds great promise, challenges can arise. These include issues related to governance, alignment of goals, and potential conflicts of interest. Effective communication and shared vision are critical to overcoming these challenges.

In conclusion, the partnership between a corporate university and a traditional university represents a powerful synergy that offers a multitude of benefits to both institutions and, by extension, to students and the broader community. By combining the strengths of academia with the practical knowledge of the corporate

world, this collaboration fosters innovation, enhances educational opportunities, and equips individuals with the skills and knowledge necessary for success in an ever-evolving global economy. As these partnerships continue to evolve and thrive, they will undoubtedly play a crucial role in shaping the future of education, workforce development, and the overall advancement of society.

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